

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND DATA ANALYTICS IN THE US-CHINA RIVALRY: STRATEGIC IMPLICATIONS FOR FOREIGN POLICY, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND GLOBAL DIPLOMACY IN THE DIGITAL AGE

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Data Analytics (Big Data) are two interconnected technologies that have achieved significant importance in the contemporary age of technology. AI is an electronic machine made with human intelligence simulation. These artificial machines can think, learn, and solve problems like humans and assist policymakers in investigating information sources, social media, economic indicators, and geopolitical events. This research investigates the influences of AI and BD on the foreign policy decision-making process of the United States and China. Both these countries have amalgamated said technologies into their diplomatic frameworks. The AI Algorithm and BD Analytics are key in collecting information on intelligence affairs and implementing diplomatic strategy. The research question of this study is “How does the usage of Artificial Intelligence and Data Analytics create an influence on the Foreign-Policy decision-making process and what simultaneous challenges can these technologies bring while gathering intelligence data”. The theory applied to this research is “Realism” as a tool for a better understanding of the influence of these modern technologies on foreign policy decision-making processes of both countries. The scholarly sources of Articles, dissertations, research papers, and reports as a source of research methodology. Moreover, the study's findings will shed light on the evolving landscape of IR due to the contemporary diplomatic policies of China and the aggressive foreign policy of the United States.

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence is the advanced form of computing systems that requires human intelligence to understand problem-solving, think, and learn. Data Analytics is large data sets that require traditional data processing methods. It has the capacity for data collection, storage, and analysis of data to extract the inner patterns. AI comprises Algorithms, models, and robots capable of performing tasks automatically. This research paper sheds light on the different narratives in increasing competition between the United States and China in the Age of Artificial Intelligence and Data Analytics, The distinct approaches, preferences, and challenges. Artificial intelligence and Data Analytics are crucial nowadays because their positive use can assist military and economic powers. "Artificial Intelligence can also be used in the private sector for business purposes to provide high-quality service levels. This technology helps in monitoring individual people and the risk of cyber-attacks." The competition between the United States and the People's Republic of China has increased the utilization of Artificial intelligence and Data Analytics in its multiple sectors for security purposes.

Some areas are important according to the perspectives of scholars of international relations. Both powers use AI to automate the decision-making processes, particularly regarding the use of nuclear capability and its stability. This technology can deeply affect the decision-making processes in both foreign and security policies. Artificial Intelligence in modern weapon systems as well. Lethal autonomous weapons are significant systems that advanced the form of technological systems

Methodology

This research through a literature review to understand the existing research on Artificial Intelligence and Data Analytics Analytics, theories, and the influences of the foreign policy decision-making process. Furthermore, comparative research of case studies for a better comprehension of the dynamics of Artificial Intelligence and the competitiveness between two rival states. In addition, the qualitative method in the concerned research. The official government reports and publications understand the comparative approaches taken by the United States and China.

Literature Review

Artificial Intelligence and Data Analytics are viable for international trade and diplomacy. According to the latest research, "Artificial Intelligence and Data Analytics are also crucial for cross-border trade because they depend on huge data. Some important rules in international trade flow are governing the digital economy". "China is a great competitor to the United States in producing AI research work deploying the technology in its all sectors. China has been a great follower of US laboratories in producing the latest models within the last few years. The Interest in China's geopolitical matters is also a threat to the United States. China has been using Artificial Intelligence for surveillance matters authoritatively for the detection of illegal ethnic minorities". Recent social scientists have revealed that international relations have become digital. The United States has initiated world politics and public diplomacy's digitalization process. Data Analytics analytics has become a tool for contemporary-age public diplomacy. China considers Artificial Intelligence as the main driver of its national economy. On the other hand, the US has used Artificial Intelligence in the domain of diplomacy to expose its influences on cyberspace to monitor the activities of the opponent state. According to the article of Anastasia, the United States authorities believe that gaining dominance in Artificial Intelligence can be a crucial reason to compete for the global military and economy as the greatest achievements in Artificial Intelligence have come from the United States as Google and Microsoft, which have made the way easier in the field of research. Moreover, Chat GPT and other WhatsApp and social media tools

have assisted in the research too. The technological companies of the United States accounted for 38 Percent of global companies. The United States has always maintained a leading role in the quality data collection. The United States has always played an essential role in developing electronic design automation. It has always remained the main initiator in developing higher-performance computing systems and Cloud Technology.

Artificial Intelligence Legislature in China

According to McBride and Chatzky's 2019 research, China has designed a ten-year plan "Made in China 2025" which was released with a vision to transform China into an influential player in the global market of high-tech manufacturing including Artificial Intelligence and Data Analytics . China is attempting to challenge the hegemony of the United States in technology within China's military strategy. (Brudzinski, 2004). China has developed asymmetric capabilities, which can provide a critical advantage in warfare and credible deterrence in peacetime. (Blasko, 2011).

Chinese Views on the Importance Of AI

Chinese leadership particularly President XI Jinping believes in being compulsory at the frontline in developing Artificial Intelligence and Data Analytics for both military and economic sectors in the future. Also, China's leadership believes that China has to reduce its dependence on import of International Technology. At an International Relations conference, the Vice Chair of the Foreign Affairs Committee of the National People's Congress delivered in her speech that Technological experts of China and policymakers believe in the increasing threat of Artificial Intelligence, so we have to work to prevent this threat. China's Ministry of Defense established two research Institutes on Artificial Intelligence under the National University of Defense Technology. The national-level body of China has developed international technical standards. AIDP has outlined three principles that are important in this regard. First, the principle of the human-interest state has the ultimate goal of Artificial intelligence is to assist in human welfare. Secondly, The Principle of liability forcing to maintain accountability is mandatory for both the development and deployment of Artificial Intelligence systems. Thirdly, the principle of Consistency of rights and responsibilities emphasizes that Data on one side and the commercial bodies should be capable enough to protect their intellectual property (Ding and Triolo 2018). The Transformative Consequences of Artificial Intelligence are suitable for a better comprehension of the geopolitics of international relations. The technological installations of Artificial intelligence and Data Analytics are gradually shaping the trends ranging from the United States of America and the People's Republic of China's technological hostility in the intelligent warfare among global major powers. (kapetas,2020). China is still depending on Western countries for advanced forms of technology. China lags in the production of advanced sort of semiconductors. Artificial Intelligence has strengthened surveillance activities in China because the country's most powerful institutions have controlled the entire societal matters inside it.

US-CHINA relations in the age of AI and Data Analytics

According to Xu and Albert, 2017, the Chinese government has deployed two million Internet censorship workers and around 1000 censors according to per individual site. (Et Al 2013). Artificial Intelligence reduces the requirements of laboratory citizens. Such developments in China's technological sectors worsen the US-China Relations. Adopting behavior democratic character. Victheirresident Mike Pence made a speech at the Hudson Institute in 2018 in crystalized words that the Relations between the United States and China have become more conflictual in recent years. On the contrary, the US and China will not be able to liberalize their economies while making such a move

competitive. In addition, China has given the name to its video surveillance system “Skynet” which is taking both states towards an antagonistic strategic competition. The Authoritative administration of Xi Jinping has been a cause of intensifying US-China Relations in this contemporary era. In addition, modern technology is the major source of increasing tensions has manifested itself. Specifically, China is increasing its traditional telecommunication very rapidly at both regional and global levels but It has Artificial Intelligence and Data Analytics are in their evolutionary stages and there are no exports at the regional and global levels. The priority of China for exporting these telecommunications is unclear in the wider background of China’s Foreign Policy. Yet both Beijing and Washington have considered AI and Data Analytics tools to be crucial for national security interests.

The Vision of China and its National Agenda

It is China’s extreme aspiration to surpass the United States in the production of Artificial Intelligence. The Chinese leadership is willing to enhance its economic and military competitiveness while taking advantage of AI developments. Chinese res has been is increased in Artificial Intelligence, particularly in the specialization of computer vision and speech recognition since 2016. China’s President “Xi” has declared the production of Artificial Intelligence and Robotics is mandatory for future economic and military development. The Chinese Communist Party is also trying to ensure the people that AI is a beneficial tool for the betterment of the Party and social development. With the release of the new generation development plan, China has exposed its ambition to the world community to lead it in the domain of AI by 2023 while becoming a “global AI permit center. China is installing ample funding for more AI project plans for future development. The plan of the next generation of China calls for applications to support decision-making authorities, military deduction, and defense of equipment and other plans.

The United States & AI Competitiveness

The United States does not have a national strategy to approach Artificial Intelligence like autocratic China. After the Administration of President “Barrack Obama”, the White House designed several papers to drive the United States with a coherent approach to Artificial Intelligence and Data Analytics analytics. At present, the United States is the leader in AI Technology production but the U.S. superiority in innovation is confronting its rival challenging states. The Defense Sector in the United States is producing Artificial Intelligence for many military functions. AI application models are active in defense sectors for the collection of data, cyber warfare activities, control, and monitoring, of the different kinds of military vehicles. The AI applications have already played an influential role in the operations in both Iraq and Syria.

The United States ‘Post-Cold War unipolar gave it an incredible potential enhancement to impose its security interests on other countries they had the inspiration to access its market. The United States built another domain of superiority that gave the entire world envy and restlessness with resentment. All this includes AI Models, research into cloud computing, the IT companies of the United States, and research centers laboratories and their affiliation with partner countries in producing cutting-edge AI and commercializing it. According to the latest report of HAI, The United States dominates more than double the next best countries that deal in the AI industry, newly invested AI companies, repository citations, publications, conference citations, and patents. The Foreign Policy of the United States should be rooted in this natural strength. The United States has shifted diplomacy from a traditional trade system paradigm to a modern AI Superiority is critical in advancing US interests. The evidences disclose that the AI of the United States is far beyond open and influential

than the competitiveness. Hence, The United States is required to expand its export controls from a narrow frame to a broader level.

Some Chinese companies are operational in the United States. TikTok is deeply involved in taking data on United States citizens in this regard. On the other hand, companies like Apple are taking data on Chinese citizens in China. Unique policy approaches are required for the two parallel risk sets of both super-power countries working on Artificial Intelligence and Data Analytics. China is making all possible efforts not to flow its data outside of China according to Chinese law. According to Article 37 of Chinese Cybersecurity law, individuals have to store the data in local servers or it must be processed through a security assessment before it is transferred to an international application. That is the reason why US companies face barriers to access and costs due to the restrictions imposed by the Chinese government. This is a different phenomenon from the way the Chinese government is handling the data taking regarding US citizens from the companies working in China.

New Media Factors in Both Us & China

The nation-states are the main actors in tech discourses and the news media give coverage to national tech policies. The South China Morning Post is based in Hong Kong is special administrative region of China and Washington Post is from the USA. Influential technological companies own both posts. Alibaba sponsored the South China Morning Post in 2016 and Amazon group CEO “JEF BEZOS” owned the Washington Post in 2013. These news outlets have focused on the East Asian region and North American region. These posts offer discourses for their native countries regarding AI developmental policies and schemes. However, the Washington Post is biased towards its country of origin. The United States and China both can remain in their best form to take advantage of Artificial Intelligence across societies. The monograph has described that without trade partners for Artificial Intelligence growth in America, technological innovation, research, and economic growth can be at a stagnating position shortly while China will refill the gap and create an enormous shadow for AI-inspiring countries. The International liberal democracies must establish the values and standards for AI otherwise China will chase the vacuum. The Prospering values between the Chinese Communist Party and liberal democracies represent a great hurdle to US-China collaboration on AI. Collaboration between the US and China is occurring in the field of academia and medical research. The solution to disputes over Artificial Intelligence will require new mechanisms and innovative approaches to diplomacy.

White House report indicated about the AI research, “The US government spent nearly \$ 1.1 billion on AI Research and development in 2015 while it is spending \$ 3 billion on mathematics and scientific research. If the United States considers Artificial intelligence as a tool for national security, then it must invest a financial backup equal to fifth-generation ammunition systems.

Case Studies

The Pilot Project Maven of the United States

An Innovative Pilot project program United States in the year 2017. It creates Algorithms to overcome the Data Analytics challenges and provide machine learning to reduce human burden. The United States must develop this kind of technology for the military domain to protect its national interest. It is only possible when the United States supports expansive STEM research programs to maintain its technological primacy.

The Gemini of The US

Gemini is the largest and most capable model of Artificial Intelligence made by the United States' Google research team. Gemini is made as the base for multimodality reasoning seamlessly across text, Images, video, audio, and coding. Millions of people are using the generative AI model. Many developers are using this model for new generative AI applications. Gemini is a flexible model that is driven from data centers center centers. mobilize three types of Gemini's:

- a. Gemini Ultra-Model for largest and highly complicated tasks
- b. Gemini Pro -An excellent model for scaling across multiple tasks.
- c. Gemini Nano most productive model for on-device tasks.

Gemini is the first model with a score of 90% for its performance. Also is the combination of 57 courses of mathematics, physics, history, law, medicine, and ethics, for testing both world Knowledge. The Google deep-minded Gemini is the competent model for Chat GPT while both are the generative AI models.

Chat GPT Application Model

Chat GPT is a new generation large language model that develops chats and text in response. Chat GPT is a web application for conversation networks based on neutrality. Chat GPT has a function with audio inputs that can generate speech outputs. Chat GPT has helped researchers largely daily. A productive app has reduced human tensions in studies to an optimum level.

The Brain Project of New Generation China

The social science analysts are well acquainted with China's AI technical development Program. According to China's New Generation Plan of 2017, China wants to be the main driver of AI development. The research in Chinese Institutes includes; perception similarity with humans, brain-like learning, brain-like mechanisms of memory, and brain-type control and computational systems. The practitioners of China made a detailed Survey and they declared three areas of research to assist China's brain AI program.

- a. Brain-inspired Artificial Intelligence Program (BI-AI).
- b. Brain mapping or Connectomes.
- c. Brain-Computer Interfaces.

Although the actual goal of this research is mainstream Artificial Intelligence till now, the difference is testing the brain behavior and the neurology and cal type of information.

Nature Machine Intelligence

Wang Et al, By focusing on biological and artificial intelligence, the author describes that neuro-inspired adaptability charges AI systems to gain information in an appropriate system even in unpredictable and tough environments.

Key Points of New Datasets

China's AI Export Database

The China's AI Export Database (CAIED) includes projects made from 2000 to 2017. CAIED gives an excellent analysis of 155 AI Projects donated by Chinese official institutions over 18 years. These projects are 51 countries around Asia, Africa, the Middle East, Eastern Europe, and Latin America. It shows that China has many chances to acquire global dominance. CAIED divides these projects into two more types. 1. AI Applications. 2. AI Infrastructure. The different research and case studies have highlighted that China exports AI to developing and underdeveloped countries. It has a special focus on those countries that are participating in the Belt and Road initiative across different regions.

Artificial Intelligence in International Relations

Artificial Intelligence can play a vital role in diplomacy as an assistant in the diplomatic domain of a country. It can help by giving analysis of different kinds of data, supporting decision-makers, and giving predictions for different kinds of phenomena. An Important threat to this phenomenon can be generated in the portion of International Relations, which can be in the form of an imbalance called a “Global Digital Gap”. Some great powers like the United States and China can gain ample economic gain estimates till 2030. While developing countries can have economic gains with lower rates from AI technology. Artificial Intelligence Technology will have a deep influence on international relations. Challenging new conspiracies and issues of geostrategic, giving service as a tool for the diplomats, and providing new opportunities and matters related to human rights. Artificial intelligence to the next generation with the passage of time and nothing can challenge its progress.

Skill Differences between the US and China

Despite China’s continuous endeavors for AI developments, there seems to be a sufficient gap in Artificial Intelligence skills between China and the United States. United States is the leader in AI theory and microchips. In comparison, China has come a long way and giving tough challenges to the US in AI theory, microchips, etc. Since 1991, Artificial Intelligence companies have started boosting in the United States while the first AI Company in China five years later (1996). The world’s most gigantic technological companies, like Google, Amazon, Microsoft, and IBM, were established in the United States. They have collected the best research team for the time being. The Head of Real-World Insights, David Kanter assesses that most of the AI-based Chips are built in the United States.

The United States and China have made Artificial Intelligence their national priority. From the aspect of economic development, national security concerns, and competition between great rival states. Specifically, the United States government was involved earlier than China in Making Artificial development plans. On the other hand, China started making its development plans in 2017 also; it is willing to chase its highest AI achievement goal by 2030. There are some prominent differences in the procedure of the decision-making process regarding Artificial Intelligence. The formulation strategy of the United States AI is because of their political parties, interest groups, and research organizations. In contrast, the Chinese autocratic government plays a vital role in national AI strategy deliberation making influential policies for a heavy investment in promoting AI technologies. Obama’s administration supported and invested a heavy budget in the domain of Artificial Intelligence as compared to Donald Trump's administration. Trump administration deducted 10% of the annual budget. This deduction can shift tasks that are more essential to the private sector like Google and Facebook. The White House Science and Technology Policy Office still has to fill a large number of positions. Both China and the United States Possess different sets of approaches regarding the strategic management of Artificial Intelligence. In addition, it has been trying to maintain its global supremacy. The United States has nearly 16 state departments regulating AI technology.

China is investing in technological development and flow, military development, joint construction, and societal development. Recently, launched some policies like “Guidance on Active Promotion of Internet Plus” and “Development plans on New Generation of Artificial Intelligence Industry”.

Theoretical Framework of AI Algorithms and Data Analytics

Several Theoretical frameworks AI Algorithms and Data Analytics depending on the special focus and objective of the research. Some are most relevant here in sequence.

The theory of Realism has a special application to the concerned research because the chosen topic is about the power acquisition game between the United States and China through different means while gaining economic power through increasing international trade. The two rival states have made a huge installation in the domain of technology through different Institutions for new research models and knowledge.

The Theory of Social Constructivism is applied in this research as technology constructs society and the research on Artificial Intelligence can shed light on different factors of social, cultural, and institutional that can influence the developmental programs of these technologies. Critical theory is also applied in the research that makes a question mark on the social inequalities and biases created by AI Algorithms and Data Analytics analytics. The power struggle and competition between both states has converted into an open trade war. The theory of Mercantilism is also in this research as they talk about avoiding outsourcing labor increasing local production and reducing imports and further, they declare international trade barriers mandatory to keep the economic state maintained.

Findings and Research Gap

Artificial Intelligence and Big are Data used in security affairs like surveillance detection and enhancing security expertise. Both Countries have invented enlightened systems for observing international developments. AI is a tool to monitor the views of people and sentiments, monitoring media reactions and the hot social media trends that can be influential to the foreign policy decision-making process. Artificial Intelligence also can monitor the markets, and economic progress of a country, and observe the policies that can influence international trade and business matters.

There is a requirement of ethical implications for further Installations of Artificial Intelligence in the process of foreign policy design. The element of privacy and positive use of technology is mandatory to maintain. In addition, there are cybersecurity risks are increasing day by day with the installation of Artificial Intelligence systems, the solution for this challenge is also mandatory. The global governance system is required with the increasing quantity of Data Analytics analytics and Artificial Intelligence algorithms to maintain international norms and standards.

Conclusion

In essence, the consolidation of Artificial Intelligence and Data Analytics has been conducted through a formative age for the foreign policy decision-making process of the US and China. The association of these technological advancements is so knowledgeable, which is shaping the geopolitical landscape in an isolated way. The United States has enhanced its intelligence potential while leading them to the international level. The capability to analyze a huge amount of data has made the way easier for the foreign decision-making process. In addition, it has provided solutions to counter the challenges of the process. Artificial Intelligence has been highlighted for surveillance purposes to detect rival threats, saving time and predictions in war-like situations. On the other hand, these technological advancements have brought simultaneous challenges like cybercrime, critical ethics, and some others as well. Although China has entered into the world of Artificial Intelligence, following the United States Its investment is lower in the technological world as compared to the US but both nations must combat the challenges of privacy, cybercrime threats, and the capacity for Algorithmic biases. The increasing dependence on Artificial Intelligence has regulated frameworks of foreign policy decision-making processes for the international communities. The influence of Artificial Intelligence and Data Analytics analytics on the foreign policy decision-making processes of both the United States and China is multiple. However, these technologies provide unprecedented benefits in terms of information collection and strategic

planning. They require some considerations of ethical, legal, and security imputation. The evolving dynamics of this technological advancement will continue in the form of competition between the United States and China for the acquisition of power superiority in international affairs to shape the political landscape.

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